

Understanding the veracities of psychosocioethnic influences in language education: A critical review

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Abstract

The present research is an attempt to understand the interdisciplinary study of language education through the interrelated concepts of applied linguistics, sociolinguistics, communication studies, sociocultural anthropology, cognitive and behavioural psychology. Second language pedagogy witnessed significant changes in the twentieth century as the English Language Teaching (ELT) mainstream evolves with the interdisciplinary concepts of Second Language Acquisition (SLA) and Second Language Learning (SLL) and language use. Drawing from a wide range of theoretical and empirical sources, the paper traces the historical development of language teaching approaches that view language both as a mental faculty and a social tool for communication. The review highlights how cognitive and behaviorist theories intersect with socioethnic factors in shaping language pedagogy, particularly in multilingual and multicultural contexts. Findings suggest that effective language education must integrate psychological understanding with sociocultural awareness to promote meaningful language use. The paper concludes by identifying key challenges and directions for future interdisciplinary research in SLA, especially in increasingly diverse educational environments.

Keywords cognitive ability, language use, multicultural impact, psychosocioethnic influences, Second Language Acquisition (SLA), Second Language Learning (SLL)

1. Introduction

The evolution of English language teaching as a field happened with tremendous growth and development with the changing psychosocioethnic influences on language education. Cognitive and behaviouristic psychology,

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gestaltism, anthropology, sociology, ethnography, education, and communication disciplines have influenced recent language studies (Howatt, 1984). The study of any language is influenced by the syntagmatic and paradigmatic developments in oral and written language practice. Second Language Learning (SLL) and Second Language Acquisition (SLA) theories are truly developed when the students' cognitive and language ability develops along with their informative content in relevance to their academic, professional, social, and cultural contexts. The process of communication can be successfully completed if only the speaker and listener pragmatically understand the content exchanged and responded to one another. Seeking and interpreting information is quite important in the communication process, and the level of convincing expression is also needed for the same. The ability to reveal information with sufficient language, cognition, and behaviouristic interactions reflects the significance of psychological and sociological impact in language learning. Second Language Acquisition (SLA), Second Language Learning (SLL) and the pragmatic use of language are specifically concerned about linguistic and sociolinguistic communicative competence.

Copious researches on forms and functions have been conducted in the field of SLA and SLL learning. Though applied psycholinguistics and applied sociolinguistics are commonly specified in language education curricula to exclusively study language in context to mind and society, interpersonal and group communication dynamics and the working of personal and socio affective attributes of different individual learners and the relevance of intercultural competence in academics and workplace is still to be addressed. This prevailing gap of socio-affective and socio ethnic influences in SLA research needs to be identified, and in particular, the role of English in future. This study aims to critically examine how psychological, socio-affective, and socioethnic factors interact to shape second language acquisition (SLA) and second language learning (SLL), and to explore how these interdisciplinary insights can be applied to improve pedagogical practices in multilingual and multicultural educational and professional contexts.

2. Impact of psychosocioethnic concepts in Second Language Acquisition (SLA) & Second Language Learning (SLL)

Stern (1983) illuminates the contribution of Saussurian (1916) and Bloomfieldian (1914, 1933) 'structuralism' and reflects how it is predominantly concerned with the descriptive analysis of formal language components. Bloomfield's 'behavioural objectives' are quite influential in exercising programmed language learning though it needs to incorporate an inductive approach in prespecifying the goals and objectives of language education. Language components like phonology, morphology and syntax are given much focus but it deliberately omits semantics. Skinner (1957) with his 'pigeon pecking' experiments advocated, "behaviourist theory' and described 'verbal behaviour' as speech utterances and texts and considered it as the observable object of the scientific study of language. Skinner discriminates the aspects of verbal behavior to 'parole' as it can be overtly observed and rejects 'langue' for its unscientific mental abstractions.

Skinner found that the attitudes and behaviours drive a compelling force in making the learners to accelerate towards language learning. The behavioral objectives of education led by Skinner reflected the importance of learners' attitudes, behaviours, and manners in language learning. Had Skinner experimented second language learning, leaving pigeon pecking in its own and recognized the behavioural pitfalls of learners' attitudes and behaviours in the actual classrooms and if had extended research on the sociocultural and educational grounds, he would have been ahead of his times, and his research would have been a complete study in the areas of second language pedagogy, general education, sociology, and anthropology. The attitudes and behaviours are of crucial importance as it affects the learner to propel towards procuring the habit of learning. Learning behaviour extremely sounds well in developing communication skills, as in the case of listening and hearing, reading aloud or silent reading and in displaying paralinguistic features while communicating.

In his sarcastic review of Skinner's Verbal Behaviour (1957), Chomsky, (1957) rejects the concept of behaviouristic theory and defines language study as a mental process and confines linguistics to the study of psycholinguistic competence. Further, Chomsky reflects that language is too complex and distinctive to be learnt by behavioural or general cognitive means. It can be learnt through the innate language faculty of the mind with the specific learning mechanisms aided through universal grammar modules. Chomsky put forth a new approach in language learning, devising the impact of mind in generating linguistic structures. Chomsky has founded a new era of psycholinguistics, a major offshoot of applied linguistics that is mainly influenced by cognitivism, the study of language by mind. With the purview of developing cognitive ability, Chomsky defined 'linguistic competence' and 'communicative competence', and propounded Transformational Generative Grammar which has been a new landmark in the history of psycholinguistics, particularly with reference to the process of innate language learning. Transformational Generative Grammar and Second Language Acquisition (SLA) theories much discuss on the significance of structural knowledge for linguistic competence (Krashen, 1982). Cognitivism is concerned with generating innate grammatical structures and mainly with the insurgence and importance given to structures, language pedagogy has become the major concern for developing linguistic competence. Chomsky's view of linguistic competence and performance is associated completely with the factors that revolve around cognitive psychology.

Stern (1983) expounds sociolinguistics, strongly grounded with proponents like Hymes (1979), Firth (1957) and Malinowski (1923) urged the need for interpersonal and social contexts to engage in communication activities. Further, Howatt (1984) explicates the philosophical insights of Austin (1911) and Searle (1969) and their contribution to Speech Act Theory have induced the development of the functional use of language. Firth (1957) largely influenced by the ethnographical study of Malinowski (1923) asserted the role of language in functional and social contexts. Labov's (1972) convictions on the use of language in social contexts and his seminal work

on dialectal variation of language evoked the emergence of sociolinguistic influences in language education. For Hymes (1979), Malinowski (1923), Firth (1957) and Halliday (1979), language use is related to the interactional social contexts, and the prime function of language is social activity. It is expounded that language learning is no longer an absolute cognitive activity just limited to mind, but it is more inclined to put the language into real use in any situational contexts.

Rejecting the restriction of semantics in Saussurian structuralism, Firth (1957) implies that with an emphasis on meaning, language must be studied at all levels in its context of situation. Firth's conception of the study of language is basically influenced by the anthropologist, Malinowski. On his interpretation of cultural studies with language, Malinowski (1935, Vol II: 11, cited in Stern, 1983, pp.138) reflects, "To us, the real language fact is the full utterances within its context of situation". Inspired by the social and contextual influences of Malinowski and Firth, Halliday (1979) stressed the social and functional use of language with equal emphasis on meaning and form. The prominent use of structures in any situations and their contextual meaning and functions has led to the development of the nature of language learning from structural to functional and from just functional to interactional model of language. The impact of attitudes and behavior in language learning (Skinner, 1957), the cognitive factors in developing innate language learning (Chomsky, 1965), social factors in developing context-based language learning (Hymes, 1979), and ethnic factors in understanding target language and culture (Firth, 1957) have paved the way for developing a psychosocioethnic approach to second language acquisition and second language learning.

Chomsky (1965), Krashen (1981) and many other psycholinguists inclined by cognitive theory consider that the concept of a distinct language module in the mind helps the learners to develop their linguistic knowledge. Cognitive skills are mainly oriented with the perception and thinking faculties and the process of producing, creating and generating structures with the linguistic abilities of the human brain and mind. Chomsky's influence on innate language learning is influential as the emphasis on language creativity and productivity is truly innovative and seems to be ahead of his times. But still, the psycholinguistic theories ignore the importance and need of social interaction in realia and lacks empirical evidence of the working of innate language faculty of mind for attaining native-like language competence. It has been often put to criticism for its mental abstractness of language learning, absence of social contexts and the lack of social dynamics for real communicative exchanges between people in varied situations. The interpersonal, interactional and social dynamics of second language learning and communication strategies for 'Competence' and 'Performance' are unexplored through the innate Language Acquisition Device. (LAD). When the prime concern of American linguists is mainly influenced on cognitive theory, the British linguists felt the crucial importance of social factors and realistic contexts in language teaching and learning. British linguists like Firth (1957), Halliday (1979), Hymes (1979), Wilkins (1976) and Widdowson (1983) considered that language pedagogy is not mainly concerned about generating linguistic structures through mind,

but it is thoroughly influenced by communication dealt in social environment. Stern (1983) reflects that the language pedagogy models of Spolsky (1980) and Campbell (1980) are generally influenced with various disciplines like linguistics, psychology, and sociology. Johnson (1982) elucidates that the emphasis of Campbell and Wales (1970) and Hymes (1970) on the study of language as communication has exemplified the paradigm shift of language learning from psycholinguistic to sociolinguistic approach.

The groundbreaking paradigms of psycholinguistic theories Chomsky (1965) on innate language learning and the later influences of Krashen (1981) on unconscious language acquisition has evoked special interest in understanding the concept of implicit language learning. The psychological view of language learning is mostly associated with the mental processes of learning. The popular five hypotheses of Krashen (1981, 1982) namely, the Acquisition – Learning hypothesis, the Natural Order Hypothesis, the Monitor Hypothesis and the Input Hypothesis and the Affective Filter Hypothesis are influenced with the framework of early psycholinguistic models, but it is still under increasing criticisms for their conscious learning and subconscious acquisition process and led to empirical issues in language teaching. The acquisition-learning hypothesis claims conscious learning and subconscious acquisition as the two psycholinguistic processes that drive second language acquisition. Krashen's (1981) controversial view is that these two are separate processes and communicative competence can be acquired through subconscious acquisition. The monitor hypothesis states how conscious learning is monitored to develop meaning-focused, communicative tasks. Krashen (1981) distinguishes the process of language learning and acquisition through Monitor, a construct that edits and controls functions during language study. The natural order hypothesis is determined by inbuilt syllabus derived from the nature of target language.

When teaching and learning techniques are adjusted and made flexible to develop comprehensive ability, the L2 speakers can learn the content through bilingual approaches and could acquire the target language too. McLaughlin (1978) explicates the relationship between bilingualism and cognitive functioning and metalinguistic awareness of the children, and how their second language learning is affected through their different linguistic and socioeconomic backgrounds. The process of immersion in content language teaching can be successful if the pedagogical techniques are adjusted and flexible. When no pedagogical adjustments of flexibility are done through immersion method and made the students learn the language and content through 'its own means, 'submersion' occurs. (Krashen, 1985, pp. 81). Further, it relates to the results of French Immersion Programmes in Canada for their failure to promote accurate productive skills as grammar and lexis is considerably varied. By defining the concept of immersion method in second language learning, Krashen reflects that immersion can maximize the students' comprehension of both the target language and the content material. Immersion can be made in both 'formal' early and late education. Research on SLA through content-based language learning substantiates that 'early immersion' or 'late immersion' can be better

developed through immersion, with the aid of bilingual teaching. This bilingual immersion approach is revised through spending additional care and time to improvise comprehensive ability of content-based language learning through conducting memorization and content revision activities and special teaching hours, daily and weekly tests, writing assignments on the topics related to the instructional contents and collecting more information on the innovative topics related to the subject are encouraged through the inhouse 'sheltered classrooms' in US.

Krashen's (1981, 1982 & 1985) research on learning and acquisition has drawn more contentions on the exposure to comprehensible input and language production activities. Krashen refers language learning as a conscious process and acquisition as an unconscious process. Krashen claims acquisition being an unconscious process is more important than conscious learning. Stern (1983) envisages that much influenced with the behaviouristic, neo-behaviouristic and psychological perspectives, Carroll (1953) identifies imitation, repetition, memorization, and habitual practice as conscious learning process for second language learning. As memorization and the retention of language content are the core mental activities associated with the psychological aspects of language learning, Comprehensible Input (CI) remains and accelerates itself as a very substantial cognitive factor to engage in communication production activities. Sheen (1994) analyzes that mere exposure to comprehensible input is not sufficient unless the student is involved in task production activities. Sheen asserts that no research findings demonstrate that exposure to comprehensible input alone in the formal language classroom is sufficient to bring about substantial levels of second language acquisition, whether the learners are involved with production or not. Emphasizing on the actual use of productive skills, Swain (1995) commends for the performance of language output activities and states that mere chances of comprehensible input cannot lead to language productivity.

As the ELT classrooms are concerned with concrete and explicit learning of structures, the contribution of Krashen's implicit language acquisition is not well received in academia and the Input hypothesis are often targeted as they are completely neither empirical nor proven in the actual classrooms. Krashen's Comprehensible Input theory has been overlooked by the second language learning experts due to his intricate style of presenting his hypothesis and his lack of research on L2 learner's individual learning differences in terms of their applying different learning strategies and styles (Sheen 1994; Swain, 1995). Although it seems that the learners are not much immediately affected by the comprehensible input, continuous exposure to language receptivity does really influence their language productivity. Though Krashen's Input hypotheses are not proven with intensive study, it cannot be easily ignored or dismissed as his assumptions on implicit and monitored learning are grounded with much value in SLA research. It must be noted that all the teachings and learnings cannot happen in the classrooms itself. Some students may immediately respond and indulge in language comprehension and production activities. But most students take indefinite time and put their effort in processing their individual language receptivity and knowledge construction abilities,

they do possess different abstract mental capabilities that help them yield for language productivity and knowledge enhancement. It can be observed that in any overcrowded classroom, all the teachers may not be able to monitor or develop the innate language capabilities and communication skills of all the students. Hence it becomes nearly impossible for them to teach or examine the implicit language learning skills of the students. But the teachers who include implicit learning in their pedagogical practices will evidently witness the innate processing of metalinguistic and metacognitive abilities through their implicit language learning in a typical ELT classroom.

The very unresolved answer to the question whether learning language is a cognitive or social task remains to be the matter of sheer complexity as vivid voices from psycholinguistics claim it to be the task of perception (Chomsky, 1965; Krashen, 1981), while sociolinguists, ethnolinguists and anthropologists reflect it as the task of social and contextual use as they trust language use is for real communication (Habermas, 1970; Hymes, 1979; Munby, 1978; Wilkins, 1976; Widdowson, 1983). Several ELT studies in the last century are oriented towards experimenting forms, functions, and situations to language teaching. The influence of Firth (1957), Hymes (1979), Brumfit (1979) and Widdowson (1983) on the social contextual and functional use of language has dominated the British tradition of linguistics and quickly spread to several continents and now it assumes to be the strongest hold in both situational and functional use of language teaching. The socioethnic value to language learning emerged as an essential requirement to understand the real use of language in parallel to the psycholinguistic approach to language learning.

The psychological and pedagogical implications of the research of Rivers (1964) recommend communicative interaction and emphasize the shift from form to functional use of language in a sociocultural context. Discriminating the role of memorization and repetition and learning structures, Rivers asserts that the process of language and communication involves a relationship between individuals and not merely the memorization and repetition of phrases and the practicing of structure. Rivers affirms the role of learners' perception, emotions and motivation in language learning and suggests interactional communication in realia. Littlewood (1981) emphasizes the role of motivation, interest and opportunity and a conducive language learning atmosphere to encourage interpersonal relationships among the learners. While discussing the use of the target language in the classroom, Littlewood exemplifies the use of the second language learning strategies through explicit and implicit learning. Mitchell & Myles (1998) consider the use of both explicit and implicit learning for second language instructional practices. It is suggested that the balance of both first and second language is needed, and the target language can be learnt through applying metalinguistic and metacognitive strategies. The syntactic features like parts of speech, sentence patterns and types, semantics and discourse can be implicitly or explicitly learned. However, for successful and meaningful communication, the ingrained innate and acquired language skills need to be put in real practice in any situational contexts. Ansarin, Yaghoubi, & Saeedi (2022) explicate the importance of cognitive abilities and

mental processing in memorizing, storing and retrieving knowledge and information. The semantic processing and the affect of first language on the second language or vice versa can be possible through the ingrained abilities of the learner and even when it is explicitly put in practice, the students tend to develop the processing of language, knowledge and communication skills through their cognitive engagements and subsequent interactions with the peers.

Stern's (1992) language pedagogy model is influenced by multidisciplinary approach and operates with four key concepts: language, learning, teaching, and context. Stern reflects that the key concept of the nature of language can be drawn through disciplines like linguistics, psycholinguistics, sociolinguistics, anthropology, and language education. The concept of teaching and learning entails understanding the role of the teacher and learner and how the theory does interpret the nature of the process of teaching and learning. The role of context is essentially significant as it describes the use of language in context to political, social, cultural, and educational background. The pedagogical context of language teaching interprets its stand and relevance to the history of language teaching, educational theory and any research analysis needs to be done on its theoretical development and evaluation. Discussing the proceedings and practical issues involved in implementing the curriculum, Stern (1992) suggests small-scale to large scale try-outs and reflects on the preparation of learning materials, disseminating relevant information about the curriculum, planning faculty and student development training programmes and the real intention of the processing of the curriculum design.

Any language learning theories should be transferred to practice and the learners' actual language learning difficulties and learning experiences should be informed to revise theories. As Stern (1983, pp. 47) adopts a multidisciplinary approach to second language education, includes anthropology and considers that "the basic pedagogical concept operates from translating theory to practice and in turn should get more informed and revised from practice to theory". Yalden (1983) asserts the influence of disciplines like psychology, sociology, and educational theories in second language learning. Recent language learning practices are totally attributed to the domains of psychosocioethnic influences on any contextual situations. Conceptual and verbal learning, skill learning, and socio-affective learning are the three major psychological categories used to define the educational objectives of a course (Stern, 1983). Klapper (2003) claims that there is no single and complete model for cognitive, acquisition and learning theories but still distinguishes the use of different approaches and models of language learning and skills acquisition and explains how its move from declarative to procedural knowledge has affected Presentation, Practice and Production (PPP) activities and complies with the fact that how it can be observed rather than to completely reject it. Brumfit (1979) and Johnson (1982) stresses language learning through communicating with various available resources and then the PPP teaching strategy can be practiced and drilled with the appropriate structures and skills.

With Affective filter hypothesis, Krashen (1982, 1985) advocates learners' low motivation, lack of confidence, little or no interest and high

anxiety affects their second language learning. Language teachers and learners should identify their positive and negative emotions and intentions that affect motivation to language learning. Learners need to be provided with a conducive learning environment, their self-esteem should not be at stake, and they should be given sufficient time and space to kindle their interest and motivation in second language learning. The empirical studies of Gardner and Lambert (1972), Gardner (1979), Gardner and Smythe (1981) focused on learners' social attitudes, values, and the motivation in relation to learning problems, strategies, styles, and outcome. Gardner (1979) finds attitudes and motivation as the main cause for more or less successful learning whereas Burstall (1974) reflects on successful early learning promotes successful later learning and more positive attitudes. Burstall's research team of the National Foundation for Educational Research (NFER) specifically analyzed the significance of positive attitudes of teachers and headmasters that immediately affect and improvise the process of language learning in the primary level education. Thus, the focus on institutional factors to language teaching and learning can be decided through involving all the key players in education and their learning preferences and strategies can be analyzed through conducting attitude test and eliciting open-ended expressions.

The content categories of any course comprising language education and communication studies imply the necessity of learning linguistic content and perform communication activities with sufficient knowledge of culture and ethics to enable the learners to display their positive personal attributes with clarity, consistency and elegance in their performance. Gardner-Lambert (1972) and Burstall (1974) studies investigated attitudes and values towards target group, target language, target language learning and general language learning and its influences on learning problems and outcomes. The position of second language learning is much equated to the first language in terms of educational, social, cultural, economic and political factors. Second language learning is strongly influenced through integrative motivation and instrumental motivation. As learner's personality factors are influenced by the social context, their learning behaviour and motive reflects the choice between integrative and instrumental motivation. Instrumental motivation is specifically reflected when the target language is likely to bring job prospects and economic advancement. The willingness to communicate in a second language correlates with instrumental motivation as it stimulates learner to confidently use English for survival purposes.

Schumann (1978, 1986) conceptualizes second language learning through social and psychological factors. The social factor refers how the learner group is related to the target language group. The psychological factors indicate the personal reflections of the learner to the language, culture, and learning environment and how it relates learner's reaction to the target language group. Schumann favours naturalistic language learning as it is concerned with the process of acculturation. In understanding the attitudes and emotional learning difficulties of the individual, psychoanalytic research is quite necessary as it probes to observe and introspect the lifestyle, personality and affective factors related to second language

learning. Psychoanalysis helps to observe individual psychological perspectives, challenges, difficulties, and problems related to second language learning. Schumann's acculturation model elucidates the attitudinal differences and the influence of social perceptions for and against second language learning. Further, Schumann explains integration strategies and the tendency of the learners to adopt one of three integration strategies to learn target language and culture – assimilating through target language and culture, rejecting to learn the target language and culture, and adapting to accept but with varying degrees of perception. Schumann refers the prevailing differences in subordinate group and dominant group and their reservation on target group and culture invokes them to learn or not to learn a language.

Schuman (1978, 1986) claims that the affective and positive personality characteristic features of an individual provide essential attributes and instigates language aptitude and cognitive skills. Empathy, language ego, acceptability, flexibility, permeability, need achievement, goal orientation, intrinsic motivation, positive learning attitudes promote necessary skills and conditions to successful language learning. Schumann considers empathy as positively associated with integrative motivation and negatively to the concept of authoritarianism, ethnocentrism and dogmatism. Stern (1983) reflects on the concept of empathy – the willingness to identify and relate with the target group for developing group specific attitudes to native like pronunciation skills. The research studies on authoritarianism, egocentrism, dogmatism, Machiavellianism and need achievement explored by Gardner-Lambert's personality test battery assessments, provide a negative correlation with integrative motive and successful language learning (Gardner & Lambert, 1972). Due to the different personal traits of the character, and to the different levels of learning interests, needs, and values, learners' motivation is positively or negatively correlated. And, given to their different educational, cultural, socioeconomic backgrounds, and to the fluctuating political conditions and environment of the state, learners attitudes and motivation towards learning invariably varies. Durkheim's (1951) analysis on anomie, a concept that reflects the disoriented status of the individual in society, reflects openness and flexibility and is positively correlated with second language learning. Due to some individual differences, when the learners feel isolated and distanced from social norms, they seek refuge in language learning and particularly gain solace in reading literature and invariably consider it as an aid in their seclusion. Esmailpour & Babae (2025) distinguishes the diverse characteristic traits of introvert and extroverts and explicates how different personalities influence the process of individual learning. Introverts are able to perform better as they are very attentive, observing and organized. This helps them to be capable enough to think, generate more ideas and express without stress or anxiety. But it can also be noted that extroverts are known for their readiness and willingness to participate and communicate instantly with their preconceived knowledge. Due to different personality attributes, contextual influences and to the different learning environments, students apply different learning skills, strategies and styles to develop their knowledge and communication capabilities.

Naiman et al. (1978) distinguishes the personality traits of good language learners as the one who are always highly aspired and goal oriented are positively involved in the process of language learning. Social, cultural and emotional influences impel the learner to positively or negatively react to the target group, language and learning environment. 'Tolerance of ambiguity' is a personality variable of a good language learner. The tendency to persevere and being flexible in the situation of complexity and the ability to overcome anxiety and frustration is a good indicator of stabilizing emotions for need achievement and positive efforts in language learning. 'Intolerance of ambiguity' can be associated with the ethnocentric traits of authoritarianism and dogmatism. While discussing the impact of personality and the attitudinal differences pertaining to the psychology of individuals, Naiman et al. reflects on the essentiality to understand the emotional difficulties of language learning and attitudes of the learners to languages and their social perceptions to target language learning. Jung's (1923) distinction between introversion and extroversion, measured by Eysenck (1970) refers introversion as the tendency to be more inhibited with inner thoughts and feelings, often found to be reserved and withdrawn from social interaction; and extroversion to be the tendency to be social, outgoing and uninhibited and ready to involve and interact with others. Both the attitudes of introversion and extroversion can be quite valuable as the former invokes systematic study of a language, while the latter promotes developing interpersonal and communication skills. Extroversion traits are positively associated with the personality variables of good language learner and regarded as an appropriate strategy to develop interpersonal communication skills (Naiman et al. 1978, Stern, 1983).

Larson and Smalley (1972) consider 'culture shock' and 'culture stress' to the disorientation and discomfort of the learner to adopt and sustain in unfamiliar target culture. While discussing adopting necessary and flexible changes in personality development, Ausubel, Sullivan & Ives (1980) discuss the distinction between learning condition, satellization and desatellization. Children have a more permeable language ego and undergo dependent or satellization phase as a condition, and adults need to accept 'infantile status' or 'loss of adult status' to involve in second language learning. Willingness or refusal to acquire and to learn a second language can be attributed to language ego. It is suggested that in early learning, language ego is found to be void whereas in later learning, language ego is found along with personality differences to readily accept or refuse to learn a language. The acculturation model of Schumann (1978) depicts the social perception of the learners and their interest and disinterest and willingness and unwillingness to learn the target language. The influence of the acculturation model on the nature of the learner and their learning tendencies and the strategies of assimilation, adaptation and rejection to the target language and culture reflects the learner characteristics of being in a state of acceptance, supporting, inability to communicate or even aversion to target language. The strong support of the learner to adapt target language reflects the crucial need and significance of the target language in learners socioeconomic development in target contexts.

Gestalt psychology opposed associationism and behaviourism. Its emphasis on perceptual and cognitive learning skills implies developing cognitive approaches to learning. Gagne (1977) includes behavioural as well as cognitive concepts in developing various kinds of learning. Mclaughlin (1978) suggests language acquisition process would be more impulsive if that includes both linguistic knowledge and behaviour of the child. The effect of culture on society pervades through communication behaviour and the attitudes of an individual. Valette's (1969) specification of behaviour and content in second language teaching is one of the innovative studies for including kinesics, culture, literature and communication as key components besides language skills, linguistic content, and orthography. The realm of language use is under the domain of communication system where linguistics is a part of it. The impact of culture on society and communication is generally found to be very illuminating in the practical use of language. As language is affected by society and culture, it is evident that the whole communication system is distinguished through the contextual use of language.

Gedbhard & Harman (2011) reflects on the impact of Bakthin (1981), Halliday (1979) and Vygotsky (1978) in Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) and New Literacy Studies (NLS), besides the psychological orientations of Krashen to L2 literacy. Cognitive skills are apparent in inducing abstract terms with or without grammar. With the prevailing conditions of human thought, language elements delve to function with non-restrained linguistic knowledge. Vygotsky's (1978) concept of monologic and mono-consciousness to discourse and Bakthin's (1981) orientation of dialogic and poly-consciousness to discourse reflects the progressive development of the individual to social interaction as well as preparing themselves to their ontological and epistemological engagement in society. The role of language in mediating cognition and the influence of sociocultural theoretical concepts in language and cognitive development is to be essentially explored in actual classrooms and realia. Swain and Lapkin (2011) reflect on the process of languaging in mediating and regulating cognition processes. Language processing and production activities can be solely interpreted through their role in mediating, regulating the effect of externalization and internalization, recalling, and creating knowledge for social interaction (Vygotsky, 1978). With the sociocultural perspectives of Vygotsky (1978) on collaborative learning and social interaction, Hogan & Tudge (1999) reflects on knowledge construction through peer learning. Peer learning helps to understand the strength and weakness of the learners, and they can mutually support one another to improve their language and communicative skills. The participation and performances of the learners can be continuously monitored and revised through their collaboration and social interaction activities. The semantic and pragmatic use of language in communication has been a crucial factor of learners' critical understanding of real communication as it helps to convey meaning and to interact in any situation.

The status of English as a global lingua franca rest on the use of its speakers and to their culture with diverse contexts. Weinstein, Tomlison-

Clarke and Curran (2004) discuss diverse views and approaches for gaining multicultural competence and expounds the beliefs and values that promote Culturally Responsive Classroom Management (CRCM). Weinstein, Tomlison-Clarke and Curran focus on conceptualizing CRCM by recognizing one's own ethnocentrism; understanding students' cultural background; understanding the social, economic and political contexts; and the willingness to use English as a language in multicultural environment. Learners need to learn and use English to convey their thought and expressions with good clarity but their mastery in language structures and expertise in communication need not be extremely demanded. In this context, McKay (2003) argues that many bilingual users of English do not need or want to acquire native-like competence. Alptekin (2010) stresses accommodating biculturalism with bilingualism for gaining multicompetence in language education. Dewaele (2005) stresses on the impact of psychological and emotional expressions and dimensions in second language acquisition and learning as it is crucial to stimulate personal identity and to promote sociocultural competence. Aguilar (2009) and Byram (1997) reflect on the implementation of Intercultural Communicative Competence (ICC) and its effect on foreign language teaching on the personal and social grounds of an individual to develop learner autonomy in realizing personal identity and fostering social interaction. As today the realm of ELT and the essentialities of ESL and EFL lies in engaging with the social and cultural factors that induce developing language and communication skills, socioethnic approaches persistently focus on survival-based learning and much familiarizes itself for developing the capability to communicate in the present and target academic, professional, and sociocultural situations.

The relevance of social and cultural influences in language learning reflects the identity of learner in the respective ESL/EFL learning environment. McKay (2003) highlights on the socioethnic dimensions of language learning where the multilingual and diverse cultural use of language and learning challenges the restricted use of monolingual users. Gentil (2011) highlights on the need of multilingual writers to adopt biliteracy perspective of both literacy and bilingualism to develop and use genre expertise in more than one language. This will help both the teachers and students to adopt bilingual teaching and learning in the ESL/EFL classes. Brady and Shinohara (2000) stresses on the importance of processing and embedding communication skills with transculturation to adapt socio-cultural identity in classroom learning and to be extended outside the classroom through the use of emails and internet-based pedagogy. Bowers (1986) opines that retrospective development of ELT is not from the psycholinguistic end of their profession but rather from the sociological influences from the ELT classrooms. ELT today is engrossed with multilingual and multicultural identity of the nonnative English speakers. The role of ELT in multicontextual, international, social, and business settings has made it to develop the intercultural communicative competence of the learners. Moreover, the socioethnic influences for seeking higher education and career enhancement have made the learners to engage in

open tasks to develop adequate competence in both formal and social English communication (Fareen, 2013).

Stern (1983) observes that affective and personality factors have been much less interpreted than cognitive aspects to language learning. It is pertinent to explore the sources of ESL and EFL learning motivation, psychological, social and cultural needs of the general English classroom. Li (1998) stresses teacher education and EFL context oriented educational awareness, research and practice in any countries for developing new pragmatic theories to ensure its implementation with the academic, social, and cultural contexts. Liu (1998) emphasizes the need to create cultural awareness and understanding and to be incorporated as a component of TESOL education programmes for developing competence in intercultural communication. Liu discusses the TESOL teacher education programmes in NABA countries and compares the academic, social and cultural contexts of ELT in Asia. Liu reports the English teaching in Asia is product-oriented and teacher centered, and, in the West, it is process oriented and engrossed with the learner-centered methodology. The product and process approaches to learning need to be very purpose-specific and should braid with the integrated approaches of form, function and interactional model of language learning. And with the change of principles and practice to teaching and culture, both the TESOL and the international orientations accommodates intercultural competence and language understanding.

The popularity of English as a global language and its indispensable role in opening global education and employment opportunities has created immense need and demand of English for seeking higher education and job placements (Fareen, 2022). This has augmented to understand the course specificity - learning English for seeking placements in higher education as English for Academic Purposes (EAP) and learning English for seeking placements at work as English for Placement Purposes (EPP). English for Placement Purposes (EPP) and learner-centered approaches to learning has led to the special development and orientation of conducting needs analysis to examine the actual needs of the learner and their learning requirements in the present academic and target job situational contexts (Fareen, 2021). In tandem to the target learning requirements of the students in higher educational institutions, 'graduate job readiness' must be focused on the academic curricula. As English for Placement Purposes (EPP) courses specify specific language needs of the students, learning processes need to be much explored to probe the different learning interests, attitudes and differences in developing verbal and nonverbal communication skills and in developing the overall personality of the individual students. As it is crucial to follow-up the effective use of English communication skills in twenty first century cosmopolitan academic and workplace, socio-affective and sociocultural positive attributes of individual for developing interpersonal and intercultural communicative competence is warranted.

3. Conclusions

In the present study, the impact of cognitive and behaviouristic psychological and socio-affective and sociocultural influences on language and communication is explored to understand the real use of language

learning in multilingual and multicultural contexts. Being, English the most sought language in every sphere of survival communication, the capability to perform in formal, social, and cultural contexts needs to be encouraged through the broad spectrum of radical, cognitive, affective, and persuasive processes of learning. Language pedagogy in the mainstream nonnative contexts is truly attributed to the role of affective, cultural and social understanding of the masses. The socioethnic values add to the change in language and communication behaviours. Further, the advent of MNC companies stressed the need for multilingualism and multiculturalism for displaying multilinguistic and multicompetence skills. As English is fast-tracking with real and virtual communication modes since post pandemic, its engagement with the global personnel in varied multilingual and multicultural academic and workplace environment can be evidently noted. As most educational institutions and organizations are engrossed with a multilingual and multicultural environment, most professionals have different exposure to social and cultural understanding and their assimilation to different cultures reflects diverse socializing abilities. In this digital age, English communication is perpetually developing amid different academics and workplace multicultural contexts. Thus, it can be widely observed in the present international ELT scenario, the influence of ethnography and convivial communication in language education is inevitable in promoting real time communication in real situational contexts.

To expand the role of English in future, English for Placement Purposes (EPP) courses need to be specifically acknowledged and put in practice in present English communication studies. Apparently in focus to sustain English as a global language for international communication and to prepare the graduates for their academic, research and job readiness, English language curricula in higher education needs to be specified with relevant genre, skills, task and competency-based approaches to develop English proficiency, business and technical communication skills. Course modules on developing effective verbal and nonverbal communication skills, interpersonal and group communication dynamics and employability skills needs to be essentially specified in the English communication syllabi. Being effective English communication is indispensably considered as the crucial skill required for employability in MNC companies, prospective employees' discourse and strategic competence has been specifically expected to engage in HR discussions and job interviews in the recruitment process; team led project-oriented discussions and presentations in the business meetings; and marketing and sales led conversations in client-connect colloquiums. In this context, the prospective employees need to groom with necessary technical knowledge and English communication abilities to engage in oral communication activities like conversation, discussions, presentations and interviews and written communication activities like writing short messages, business emails and project reports that could help them become employable and sustainable in their career. As the global industries expect their employees to display positive attitudes and assertive behaviour, soft skills with necessary nonverbal cues are to be practiced with English communication skills. Higher education is in dire need to integrate

employability skills and to provide sufficient training in discursive skills, soft skills and personality development through their language and communication syllabuses. It is now high time that the higher education should move forward to adopt institutional-industrial partnership and collaborate with leading MNC's to prepare the students for job placements. To make it earnestly possible, employability skills and needs based syllabuses are to be incorporated as a necessary component to constitute in the English communication courses in the present university language curriculum.

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